

The Hidden Appendix: A Rare Encounter with De Garengeot Hernia

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ABSTRACT

De Garengeot hernia is a rare subtype of femoral hernia characterized by the presence of the appendix within the femoral canal. First described in 1731, this condition accounts for only 0.5% to 3.3% of femoral hernias, with acute appendicitis occurring in approximately 0.13%–1% of all cases. The pathophysiology of this entity remains debated, with hypotheses suggesting either displacement due to anatomical variations or abnormal embryological development. Patients often present with an irreducible, tender groin mass, sometimes accompanied by fever and systemic symptoms, making preoperative diagnosis challenging.

Imaging modalities such as computed tomography (CT) scans can aid in diagnosis, though many cases are only identified intraoperatively. Standard treatment involves emergency appendectomy and femoral herniorrhaphy, with the surgical approach determined by intraoperative findings. Open surgery remains the preferred method, particularly in cases of perforation, though laparoscopic techniques have been explored. The use of mesh in hernia repair is debated, especially in the presence of infection.

This case report highlights a patient who presented with a tender, irreducible groin mass, initially suspected as an obstructed femoral hernia. Imaging failed to confirm the diagnosis, and intraoperative findings revealed a de Garengeot hernia with acute appendicitis. The patient underwent successful appendectomy and non-mesh hernia repair, with an uneventful postoperative recovery.

Due to its rarity and nonspecific presentation, De Garengeot hernia remains a diagnostic and surgical challenge. Heightened clinical suspicion, timely imaging, and early surgical intervention are crucial for optimizing

outcomes. This case underscores the importance of considering this rare entity in patients presenting with groin masses, particularly in elderly women, to prevent delays in diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: De Garengot hernia, Femoral hernia, Acute appendicitis, Surgical management

INTRODUCTION

Femoral hernias are a relatively uncommon type of groin hernia, occurring more frequently in females due to their wider pelvis and relatively larger femoral canal. Despite their rarity, femoral hernias carry a significant risk of complications, including incarceration and strangulation, leading to substantial morbidity and mortality. A particularly rare entity within this category is the presence of the appendix within the femoral canal, known as a de Garengot hernia, first described in 1731 by the French surgeon René Jacques Croissant de Garengot ^[1]. This phenomenon represents only 0.5% to 3.3% of all femoral hernias, while the incidence of acute appendicitis within an external hernia is estimated at 0.13%–1% of all cases of acute appendicitis ^[2,3]. De Garengot hernia is most commonly observed in women in their sixth decade of life ^[2,4].

The underlying pathophysiology of de Garengot hernia is not completely understood, though two primary mechanisms have been proposed. One theory suggests that an anatomically large cecum may displace the appendix into the femoral canal, while another postulates that abnormal intestinal rotation during embryological development predisposes the appendix to herniation ^[5,6]. Furthermore, acute appendicitis in the femoral canal may arise through two possible mechanisms: either initial migration of the appendix followed by obstruction within the rigid femoral canal leading to incarceration and subsequent inflammation, or primary appendicitis occurring in situ before displacement into the femoral canal ^[7,8].

Diagnosing de Garengot hernia preoperatively remains a challenge, as the clinical presentation often mimics that of an obstructed femoral hernia or acute appendicitis. Unlike intra-abdominal appendicitis, which typically presents with peritoneal irritation, de Garengot hernia may lack classical peritoneal signs due to the restricted space within the femoral canal. Most cases present as an irreducible, tender groin lump, occasionally accompanied by fever, nausea, and vomiting ^[3,4]. In instances of perforation, overlying skin erythema may be observed, necessitating urgent surgical intervention.

The diagnosis is frequently made intraoperatively during surgical exploration for a suspected strangulated femoral hernia ^[5]. While preoperative imaging, including computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and ultrasonography, can aid in diagnosis, de Garengot hernia is only correctly identified preoperatively in approximately 33% of cases³. Radiological findings include a tubular structure extending from the cecum into the femoral canal, often with adjacent fat stranding ^[9-11]. Features such as wall thickening and intramural gas may indicate complicated appendicitis ^[9-11]. However, plain radiographs and routine laboratory investigations are generally nonspecific and provide limited diagnostic value^{3,7}.

Surgical management consists of emergency appendectomy and femoral herniorrhaphy ^[3,4]. Due to the frequent intraoperative diagnosis, an open approach is often preferred over laparoscopic techniques, although no standardized surgical approach has been established ^[12]. In most cases, appendectomy via the hernia sac is

sufficient; however, in cases of perforated appendicitis, a transabdominal approach may be necessary. When preoperative diagnosis is achieved, laparoscopic appendectomy combined with a totally extraperitoneal (TEP) hernia repair can be considered [13]. The use of synthetic mesh for femoral hernia repair remains controversial, as its application is discouraged in cases with abscess formation or perforation due to the risk of infection [3,14].

Postoperative complications, particularly surgical site infections, occur in 14%–29% of cases and are associated with delayed diagnosis, advanced age, and extensive tissue involvement [1,14]. Prompt recognition and early surgical intervention remain crucial to optimizing patient outcomes and minimizing postoperative morbidity. This case report aims to contribute to the existing literature by highlighting the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges associated with de Garengeot hernia, emphasizing the need for heightened clinical suspicion in patients presenting with an irreducible groin mass.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 74-year-old previously healthy female presented with a one-day history of a right-sided inguinal lump, approximately 5 cm in size. The lump was non-reducible and gradually became painful by the end of the day. There were no associated bowel symptoms, such as constipation, nausea, or vomiting, and no prior history of abdominal hernias. The patient sought medical attention due to the increasing pain and was subsequently referred to the surgical team with a provisional diagnosis of an obstructed femoral hernia.

On admission, the patient was conscious and hemodynamically stable, with a blood pressure of 120/80 mmHg, a heart rate of 120 beats per minute, and an oxygen saturation of 99%. Respiratory function was normal, with a respiratory rate of 14 cycles per minute. Physical examination revealed a tender, irreducible inguinal lump without overlying inflammatory signs. The abdomen was soft, with no signs of peritonitis. Bowel sounds were present, and digital rectal examination revealed normal stool passage. Given the risk of strangulation associated with femoral hernias, an urgent herniotomy was planned.

Initial investigations included an abdominal X-ray, which did not reveal features of intestinal obstruction. An ultrasound scan confirmed the presence of a femoral hernia but did not identify its contents. Laboratory tests, including a full blood count, showed normal leukocyte counts, hemoglobin levels, and platelet counts.

The patient was taken to the operating theater for a herniotomy via an inguinal incision. Intraoperatively, a blind-ended, tubular structure was found entrapped within the femoral canal (**Figure 1**). Further exploration revealed its connection to the cecum, confirming it as the appendix. The appendix was inflamed, swollen, and erythematous, consistent with acute appendicitis. An appendectomy was performed (**Figure 2**), followed by reduction of the cecum into its normal anatomical position. Given the risk of bacterial translocation associated with acute appendicitis, mesh was not used in the hernia repair to minimize the risk of infection.

Postoperatively, the patient had an uneventful recovery. Oral feeding was initiated on postoperative day one, and the patient was discharged on postoperative day three. At the one-week follow-up, there were no signs of infection or complications.

This case underscores the diagnostic challenge of de Garengeot hernia and highlights the importance of considering this rare entity in the differential diagnosis of an irreducible groin mass.

Figure 1: Appendix entrapped in the femoral canal

Figure 2: Appearance of inflamed, swollen appendix after appendectomy

DISCUSSION

De Garengeot hernia remains an extremely rare clinical entity, often presenting a diagnostic challenge due to its nonspecific symptoms and resemblance to other groin hernias. The majority of cases are diagnosed intraoperatively, with only a small fraction accurately identified through preoperative imaging ^[3,5]. In our case, the patient presented with a tender, irreducible groin mass without overt signs of peritonitis, consistent with prior reports of this condition.

The rarity of de Garengeot hernia is attributed to the unique anatomical position of the appendix, which normally resides in the right lower quadrant of the abdomen. Several theories have been proposed to explain its migration into the femoral canal, including variations in cecal anatomy and abnormal intestinal rotation ^[5,6]. Additionally, the pathogenesis of appendicitis within a femoral hernia remains debated, with some authors suggesting that the appendix initially displaces into the canal and subsequently develops inflammation, while others propose that appendicitis occurs in situ before displacement ^[7,8].

Preoperative imaging plays a crucial role in diagnosing de Garengeot hernia, although its sensitivity remains low. CT scans have been shown to be the most effective modality, revealing a tubular structure extending from the cecum into the femoral canal, sometimes with fat stranding or inflammatory changes ^[9-11]. In our case, ultrasound was used initially but failed to identify the appendix within the hernia sac, reinforcing the challenges associated with preoperative diagnosis.

Surgical management of de Garengeot hernia involves prompt appendectomy and hernia repair ^[3,4]. The choice of surgical approach depends on intraoperative findings, with an open approach being the most commonly employed technique due to the high frequency of intraoperative diagnoses ^[12]. Although laparoscopic techniques have been explored, their utility remains limited in cases of perforated appendicitis¹³. Additionally, the decision to use mesh for hernia repair is controversial, as mesh placement in contaminated fields increases the risk of surgical site infections ^[3,14]. In our case, due to the presence of acute appendicitis, a non-mesh repair was performed to minimize infection risk.

Postoperative outcomes are generally favorable, with most patients recovering without major complications ^[1,14]. However, delayed diagnosis can contribute to increased morbidity, particularly in cases of perforation or abscess formation. Our patient experienced an uneventful recovery, highlighting the importance of early recognition and timely surgical intervention.

In conclusion, de Garengeot hernia should be considered in the differential diagnosis of an irreducible groin mass, particularly in elderly female patients. Given its diagnostic complexity, heightened clinical suspicion, along with appropriate imaging and early surgical intervention, is essential to ensuring optimal patient outcomes.

CONCLUSION

De Garengeot hernia is a rare but clinically significant condition that presents diagnostic challenges due to its nonspecific symptoms. Given its potential for complications such as strangulation and perforated appendicitis, early recognition and prompt surgical intervention are crucial. Preoperative imaging, particularly CT scans, may

aid in diagnosis, but intraoperative identification remains common. The choice of surgical approach depends on the presence of appendicitis and contamination, with open surgery being preferred in most cases. This case reinforces the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for de Garengéot hernia in patients with irreducible groin masses. Early diagnosis and appropriate surgical management are key to minimizing morbidity and ensuring favorable patient outcomes.

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